

UHTS-LGTF

Quality Control Report

Wed Oct 3 18:21:43 CEST 2018

Summary

Run Date : 18.09.2018	Laboratory : Claus Wedekind
Instrument : HiSeq 2500	Library name : AC1
Run number : 0265	Ref. organism : Other
Flowcell : ACCBD6ANXX	Protocol : Genomic_DNA
Lane number : 4	
Run type : single read 125 cycles	

Notes :

- BaseCalling done using Illumina RTA 1.18.66.3
 - Post processing done using Illumina pipeline 2.19.1
 - For quality control purpose, each lane might be spiked with approx. 5% of phix genome sequences.
 - Adapter sequence not trimmed
 - Fastq file : contains passed AND not passed filter reads ; in header « Y » stand for « sequence is filter OUT ». Quality score is encoded in a +33 offset ASCII (Sanger like).
 - cf detail p.20 in https://support.illumina.com/content/dam/illumina-support/documents/documentation/software_documentation/bcl2fastq/bcl2fastq2_guide_15051736_v2.pdf
-

Basic Statistics

Measure	Value
Filename	AC1_S15_L004_R1_001.fastq.gz
File type	Conventional base calls
Encoding	Sanger / Illumina 1.9
Total Sequences	52118616
Sequences flagged as poor quality	2847207
Sequence length	126
%GC	46

Sequence diversity ratio [AC1]

- diversity ratio (different/all): 0.44

Sequence identification

- **Adapters**

- **Mapping Results**

Reference	Reads processed	Mapped %	One hit / one genome %	Multiple hits / one genome %	One hit / multiple genomes %	Multiple hits / multiple genomes %
EMBLdb	10000	25.20	na	na	na	na
Human	99938	10.05	0.06	0.01	0.56	9.42
Mouse	99938	9.93	0.11	0.08	2.56	7.18
Repeat_db	99938	21.74	7.83	3.68	1.43	8.80
mitochondria	99938	1.20	0.00	0.10	0.22	0.88
rRNA	99938	10.86	0.16	1.11	1.54	8.05
miRNA	99938	0.42	0.00	0.01	0.04	0.37
ncRNA	99938	1.01	0.03	0.07	0.10	0.81
Other_ncRNA	99938	3.21	0.00	0.02	2.27	0.92
Plasmids	99938	7.28	0.24	0.00	3.38	3.66
Vectors	99938	11.07	0.10	0.00	2.49	8.48
Ecoli	99938	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

PhiX	99938	0.03	0.00	0.00	0.03	0.00
Virus	99938	1.01	0.00	0.00	0.11	0.90
Adapter	99938	10.50	0.01	0.00	2.48	8.01

Per base sequence quality

Per sequence quality scores

Per base sequence content

Per sequence GC content

Per base N content

Sequence Length Distribution

Sequence Duplication Levels

Percent of seqs remaining if deduplicated 21.64%

Overrepresented sequences

Sequence	Count	Percentage	Possible Source
CGAGATCGGAAGAGCACACGTCTGAACTCCAGTCACGCCAATATCTCGTA	561035	1.0764579780859875	TruSeq Adapter, Index 6 (100% over 47bp)
AATTAAATTAGATCGGAAGAGCACACGTCTGAACTCCAGTCACGCCAATA	93903	0.18017170678515332	TruSeq Adapter, Index 6 (100% over 40bp)
TCGATAATTCACCAAGCGTTGGATTGTTACCCACTAATAGGGAACGTGA	80590	0.15462805075253724	No Hit
CGGTAAATTCACCAAGCGTTGGATTGTTACCCACTAATAGGGAACGTGA	71854	0.1378662856281525	No Hit
ACTGGAATTCACCAAGCGTTGGATTGTTACCCACTAATAGGGAACGTGA	70116	0.13453158464530218	No Hit
TACCGAATTCACCAAGCGTTGGATTGTTACCCACTAATAGGGAACGTGA	68520	0.13146933909373187	No Hit
CTCGCTCTTCCGATCTCGAGATCGGAAGAGCACACGTCTGAACTCCAGTC	68414	0.13126595687038198	Illumina Multiplexing PCR Primer 2.01 (100% over 32bp)
TCACGCTCTTCCGATCTCGAGATCGGAAGAGCACACGTCTGAACTCCAGT	61494	0.1179885513460296	Illumina Multiplexing PCR Primer 2.01 (100% over 31bp)
TAGTAAATTCACCAAGCGTTGGATTGTTACCCACTAATAGGGAACGTGA	57620	0.11055550669265661	No Hit
CTGCGAATTCACCAAGCGTTGGATTGTTACCCACTAATAGGGAACGTGA	54304	0.10419309676220105	No Hit
ATTACAATTCACCAAGCGTTGGATTGTTACCCACTAATAGGGAACGTGA	53434	0.1025238275705556	No Hit
CATATAATTCACCAAGCGTTGGATTGTTACCCACTAATAGGGAACGTGA	52211	0.10017725720115053	No Hit

Produced using part of FastQC (fastqc_v0.11.4)